

**METHODS, PROBLEMS AND DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF
TRANSLATION OF NEWSPAPER-JOURNALISTIC STYLE TEXTS.**

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Abstract: This article systematize the methods, some important issues and other essential features of translation. It also deals with several difficulties in translation of texts from English into Uzbek. In this article, lexical, grammatical, stylistic, and other aspects of texts are emphasized in translating.

Keywords: colloquialisms, oblique translation, interpretation, literal, technical, belles-lettres text.

The word "translation" seems to be simple and clear. More people consider that this is an ordinary transfer of the text from one language into another by writing or printing. In general, a concept of "translation" is multifaceted and complex. Translation is a type of professional translation that studies all the aspects of the source and target languages for the most accurate interpretation of the content. Therefore we can differentiate between literary and informative translation, on the one hand, and between written and oral translation (or interpretation), on the other hand. Literary translation considers literary texts, such as, works of fiction or poetry whose main function is to make an emotional or aesthetic impression upon the reader. Informative translation is rendering into the target language non-literary texts, the major purpose of which is to convey a certain of ideas, to inform the readers. The particular tasks inherent in the translation of literary works of each genre are more literary than linguistic. The major

challenge to the translator is to combine the maximum equivalence and the high literary merit. The translator of a belles-lettres text is considered to make a careful study of the literary trend the text belongs to, the other works of the same author, the peculiarities of his individual style and manner and so on.

We may single out translations of scientific and technical texts, of newspaper materials, official papers and some other types of texts such as public speeches, political and propaganda materials, advertisements, etc.

Translation of scientific and technical materials has the most important role to play in our age of the revolutionary technical progress. There is hardly a translator or an interpreter today who can not deal with technical matters. In technical translation the main goal is to identify the situation depicted in the original. The predominance of the referential function is a great challenge to the translator who must have a good command of the technical terms and a sufficient understanding of the subject matter to be able to give an adequate description of the situation even if this is not fully achieved in the original

Journalistic texts dealing with social or political matters are sometimes singled out among other informative materials because they may feature elements more commonly used in literary text (metaphors, similes and other stylistic devices) which cannot but influence the translator's strategy. However, they are often regarded as a kind of newspaper materials (periodicals). There are also some intermediate types. The interpreter rendering his translation by word of mouth may have the text of the original in front of him and translate it "at sight". A written translation can be made of the original recorded on the magnetic tape that can be replayed as many times as is necessary for the translator to grasp the original meaning.

Translation Methods

One common translation method is called free translation. It can be referred to as creative translation. This doesn't mean that it's inaccurate, more so that the translator doesn't focus on the syntax and style of the source language. Instead, the reproduced text will be an accurate translation of the original, but it might not exactly mirror the original's structure, grammar and register.

A similar method is called idiomatic translation, which reproduces the message of the original text by specifically using the target language's idioms and colloquialisms. This creates segments that look different and could not be translated directly, but are still very similar in meaning. Translation Techniques

In general, we recognize two main types of translation techniques: direct translation techniques and oblique translation techniques.

Direct translation techniques is used when the elements of the text being translated are similar in both the source and target languages. These elements, such as grammar and sentence structure, or particular concepts about them, can be transposed from one language to another.

Oblique translation techniques are applicable when the former is impossible, when the meaning must be changed slightly, or the grammar and style of the text must be played with to translate it. These major techniques already match to some of the overarching methods we saw earlier.

Problems and newspaper articles translation technology

Types and features of texts, the role of different types of newspaper articles in the daily life of mankind. Methods translations of newspaper articles. Grammatical, lexical, phraseological and stylistic difficulties of translation of newspaper articles.

Lexical difficulties of translation

Stylistic difficulties of translation

The difficulty of translation of set phrases and idioms

List of set expressions used in different types of newspaper articles

To communicate with others, to convince and to find information, to listen, to read and speak - those are what the life consist of and the business life especially. We cannot imagine our life without newspaper. News is a kind of "window" to the world. People can find developments, sport and fashion news from newspaper.

Difficulties in translation of newspaper articles

Very often we have to translate newspaper or magazine articles in different topics. In course of translation some questions may arise connected to the translation of newspaper headlines.

To sum it up, we should stress that contrary to the headlines of scientific and technical articles that as a rule give some insight into the main idea of the article's content and thus in a certain way are the “key” to understanding of the text, for the newspaper headlines the situation is different.

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